

Embedded LES of a turbulent thermal boundary layer over ice roughness

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ABSTRACT

The numerical prediction of ice accretion via icing codes relies on the proper estimation of the heat transfer coefficient on rough ice geometries. To understand the heat transfer physics at play, direct numerical simulations (DNS) on rough surfaces can be performed, although this results in a very expensive option if geometries obtained from different icing conditions want to be analyzed. Large eddy simulation (LES) presents itself as a less expensive option to perform such studies, giving insight into the physics of turbulence, as well as opening the possibility for calibration of roughness models. The present study verifies and validates a setup to perform embedded LES (ELES) of a zero pressure gradient incompressible flow over a flat plate with ice roughness heated to a constant wall temperature. An experimental database is used, which provides the geometries of rough plates obtained from unwrapped scans of ice shapes generated on a NACA0012 airfoil. The low-speed flow over the flat plate presents a $Re_L = 3.85 \cdot 10^5$ and $Pr = 0.729$. The verification is carried out by analyzing the effects of the mesh resolution and the domain span on wall properties such as the skin friction coefficient and Stanton number. Additionally, an analysis of turbulence-related flow statistics is performed to guarantee the proper development of turbulence. The validation shows good agreement between ELES results and experimental data, especially for the Stanton number distributions, showcasing that this setup can be used for the study of heat transfer on ice roughness.

1. Introduction

Icing codes are CFD tools that predict the location and shape of ice accretion on aircraft components exposed to icing conditions. Several icing codes exist such as DICEPS [1], FENSAP-ICE [2], LEWICE [3], PoliMice [4] and IGLOO2D [5], which effectively predict ice shapes formed by the impingement of supercooled water droplets in rime ice conditions [6], with complete freezing of impinged water droplets. On the other hand, glaze ice conditions do not favor complete freezing right upon impact due to the lack of low enough freestream temperatures or due to large amounts of droplets impinging on the surface, resulting in the formation of thin water films. The calculation of the rate of ice accretion on these water films requires performing a local mass and thermal balance on the surface [7], from which accuracy issues arise due to the necessity of properly predicting the convective heat flux in the presence of rough ice surfaces. Studies such as the one of Hansman [8] note that the local rate of ice accretion on glaze ice conditions is almost proportional to the surface convective heat transfer

coefficient HTC , meaning that icing codes need to be able to estimate this quantity with relatively high accuracy. This can be done through the use of RANS models that can take into account the ice roughness effects on the thermo-aerodynamic flow fields and surface properties such as the HTC , although these ice roughness effects are yet not well understood.

Research on the physics of flows over rough surfaces has led to experimental and numerical studies that look into correlating the statistical parameters of rough surfaces to a roughness-representative quantity, such as the equivalent sand-grain roughness height k_s , which is commonly used in roughness studies [9]. Said statistical parameters can be the root-mean-square of the surface fluctuations R_q , their skewness Sk , or an effective slope parameter, among other parameters that can be used to characterize roughness. Correlations such as the ones of Bons [10] and Flack and Schultz [11] have been elaborated and calibrated based on limited experimental databases. On the other hand, correlations such as the one of Forooghi et al. [12] are based on results of direct numerical simulations (DNS) of flows over rough

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surfaces. It is noted that in contrast to experiments, DNS provides a deeper insight into the physics of turbulence and heat transfer, which can be useful in the design of roughness correlations as evidenced in the studies of Thakkar et al. [13], Forooghi et al. [14], MacDonald et al. [15], Yang et al. [16,17], which have performed DNS on plane channel configurations featuring synthetic or experimental roughness. Plane channels constitute simplified domains with spanwise and streamwise periodicity, which results in the analysis of a surface with a unique homogeneous k_s value. Ice roughness is inherently non-homogeneous as shown in several studies [18], i.e., k_s and statistical parameters vary streamwise and the surface is exposed to growing boundary layers. This lack of streamwise periodicity can drastically increase the required computational resources for numerical studies. Cardillo et al. [19], Yuan and Piomelli [20] have performed DNS on boundary layers over homogeneous roughness, while no study has been carried out on non-homogeneous roughness surfaces. Since ice roughness presents different non-homogeneous distributions based on icing conditions and the geometry of the iced aircraft component, carrying a DNS for the study of several specific ice roughness cases could result in the usage of vast amounts of computational resources, making the elaboration and calibration of roughness correlations for icing applications very constrained.

Large eddy simulation (LES) presents an option to drastically reduce the required computational resources relative to DNS, opening the possibility of studying different ice roughness cases. LES has been applied to flows over airfoils with accreted ice, being several of these works reviewed by Stebbins et al. [21], while more recent studies are found also in Wong et al. [22], Sheidani et al. [23], and Bornhoft et al. [24]. Nevertheless, these studies look towards the impact of ice accretion over aerodynamic forces and are not meant for calibration of roughness models or the calculation of HTC on ice roughness. Related to this last topic, the study of Sotomayor-Zakharov [25] presents a methodology to perform embedded LES (ELES) on scanned ice shapes obtained from icing experiments on an airfoil. In this numerical investigation, a LES region was created around the ice rough surface located at the leading edge of the airfoil in order to resolve the turbulent flow, while the rest of the flow domain was simulated via RANS. The expected enhancement of HTC due to roughness was obtained from the numerical simulations, although without any experimental HTC measurements to validate the approach. This prompted a high interest in validating this approach using an already available experimental database, which may include HTC measurements.

The objective of the present study is to verify and validate an ELES setup for the simulation of boundary layers over non-homogeneous ice roughness. The experimental database of McCarrell et al. [26] is used as a reference for the numerical simulations since it presents unwrapped scans of ice shapes obtained on a NACA0012 airfoil, which result in flat plates with a non-homogeneous rough region. Additionally, the database presents measurements of skin friction c_f and Stanton number St (property analogous to HTC) performed on these rough plates, which are used for validation purposes. The ELES are carried out using the software ANSYS FLUENT 21R2 and are based on the geometry and flow conditions of the experiments, resulting in the simulation of an incompressible zero pressure gradient (ZPG) flow over a heated rough plate. The temperature is treated as a passive scalar, therefore, it does not have any influence on the momentum transport, i.e., no effect on the velocity field or in fluid properties such as density or dynamic viscosity. The present manuscript is organized as follows: a detailed description of the numerical setup for the ELES is presented in Section 2, followed by a description of the tested cases and flow conditions for the study included in Section 3. Results related to the verification of the setup are presented in Section 4 which describe the effects of domain size and mesh resolution, while a comparison with the experimental measurements and validation of the setup is presented in Section 5. The conclusions of the study are presented in Section 6.

Fig. 1. Experimentally obtained rough plates by McCarrell et al. [26]. Coloring displays local heights h of roughness elements. Geometries: Left: 113 012.05 (low roughness). Right: 113 012.04 (high roughness).

Fig. 2. Schematic of the experimental setup used by McCarrell et al. [26] in the heated rough plate experiments at the BSWT.

2. Numerical setup

2.1. Experimental data

The investigated surfaces were taken from the study of McClain et al. [27], which contains digital geometries of rough plates based on the unwrapped scans of ice shapes generated on a NACA0012 under icing conditions. For the experiment, these rough plates were scaled up 10 times and 3D printed in both plastic and aluminum. As an example, the 2 selected rough plates for the present numerical study are shown in Fig. 1, which present a size of 952.5 mm of streamwise length and 203.2 mm of span length. The streamwise non-homogeneous nature of ice roughness can be clearly observed, with geometry 113 012.05 presenting lower roughness levels than geometry 113 012.04.

In the experiment of McCarrell et al. [26], the rough plates were instrumented to perform measurements of the HTC via infrared cameras and surface heating, in addition to skin friction measurements, using a flow velocity 10 times slower to match the Reynolds number of the icing conditions after the scaling up procedure. The measurements were performed at the Baylor University Subsonic Wind Tunnel (BSWT) following the setup schematized in Fig. 2.

The obtained HTC measurements are presented in the form of Stanton number St vs. Reynolds number Re_x in Fig. 3 for the plastic and aluminum surfaces, being St defined by Eq. (1), while Re_x is defined by Eq. (2).

$$St = \frac{HTC}{\rho c_p U_\infty} \quad (1)$$

$$Re_x = \frac{\rho U_\infty x}{\mu} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3. Measurements of St vs. Re_x by McCarrell et al. [26] using geometries 113012.05 (low roughness) and 113012.04 (high roughness). Left: Plastic surface. Right: Aluminium surface.

Fig. 4. Flow domain for the numerical simulations.

Table 1
Conditions and flow properties for numerical simulations.

U_∞ [m/s]	ρ [kg/m ³]	μ [Pa s]	L [mm]	Re_L [-]
6.672	1.124	$1.858 \cdot 10^{-5}$	952.5	$3.85 \cdot 10^5$
T_b [K]	ΔT [K]	c_p [J/kg K]	λ [W/m K]	Pr [-]
300	10	1007	$2.565 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.729

Here, ρ is the fluid density, U_∞ is the freestream velocity, c_p is the fluid-specific heat capacity at constant pressure, μ is the fluid dynamic viscosity and x is the streamwise position, with $x = 0$ mm being at the front of the rough plate. It is noted that the surface presents an unheated region extending up to $x = 44$ mm, equivalent to a $Re_x = 0.18 \cdot 10^5$, implying a delayed formation of the thermal boundary layer relative to the velocity boundary layer. The obtained data is compared with the theoretical values of St for a laminar and turbulent boundary layer on a smooth surface with a constant heat flux and an unheated surface length $\xi = 44$ mm, being their definition presented in Eqs. (3) and (4), respectively [28], where $Pr = c_p \mu / \lambda$ is the Prandtl number, with λ being the fluid thermal conductivity. The values of the fluid properties reproduce the air conditions of the experiment, listed in Table 1 in Section 3.1.

$$St_{\text{lam,HF}} = 0.453 Re_x^{-1/2} Pr^{-0.66} \left[1 - \left(\frac{\xi}{x} \right)^{3/4} \right]^{-1/3} \quad (3)$$

$$St_{\text{turb,HF}} = 0.030 Re_x^{-1/5} Pr^{-0.40} \left[1 - \left(\frac{\xi}{x} \right)^{9/10} \right]^{-1/9} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 3 shows that the experimental data match the laminar correlation while presenting values above the smooth turbulent one after the roughness-induced transition takes place in the regions between $Re_x = 1 \cdot 10^5$ and $Re_x = 2 \cdot 10^5$. Nonetheless, in the cases with the aluminum surface, a sudden increase of St can be observed at $Re_x = 1 \cdot 10^5$. It was discussed with the authors of the experimental work that the reason behind this was the high conductivity that aluminum presents, conveying heat horizontally towards the front regions of the rough plate. This is not an effect of an apparent boundary layer transition, but rather thermal conduction, disregarded in the present study. Therefore, several differences in the experimental measurements between both types of surfaces are attributed to this conductive effect being stronger in the aluminium surface in contrast to the plastic one.

2.2. Numerical domain

The flow domain for the numerical simulations is depicted in Fig. 4, based on the reference experimental setup presented in the previous section. The domain height $\Delta H = 304.8$ mm is preserved from the experiments, while the domain span ΔZ is varied as a parameter in the present simulations, extending from $z_{\text{max}} = \Delta Z/2$ to $z_{\text{min}} = -\Delta Z/2$. The domain is divided into three subdomains: a Laminar subdomain, a LES subdomain, and a RANS subdomain, with interfaces between subdomains at locations $x = 101.6$ mm ($Re_x = 0.41 \cdot 10^5$) and at $x = 1117.6$ mm ($Re_x = 4.51 \cdot 10^5$). An analysis of the effect of the location of the interfaces on the simulation results is presented in Appendix. It can be seen that the x coordinate is set to be zero at the beginning of the rough plate, which in the experiments extends up to $x = 952.5$ mm ($Re_x = 3.85 \cdot 10^5$). This measure is taken as the reference length scale $L = 952.5$ mm. Nevertheless, the flat plate is extended with a smooth zone from $x = 952.5$ up to $x = 4064.0$ mm ($Re_x = 16.41 \cdot 10^5$) for numerical reasons. The rough plate and its extension are no-slip walls set at a constant wall temperature T_w . This approach simplifies the analysis compared to applying a prescribed heat flux to the base of the rough plate, as in the experiment, which would involve modeling heat conductivity in the solid body. Although modeling solid body conduction in the simulation could capture the differences exhibited by the materials used in the experiments in the laminar region, this is out of the scope of the present study. Moreover, it is expected that considering an isothermal boundary condition instead of a constant heat flux one may have a strong influence on the results in regions where the boundary layer is laminar while presenting minimum influence on the turbulent boundary layer [28], which develops on the rough region. This is supported by comparing Eqs. (3) and (4) with their isothermal counterpart, defined in Eqs. (5) and (6). The St in the laminar region differs by $\sim 36\%$, while in the turbulent region the difference falls down to $\sim 4\%$. The isothermal and constant heat flux trends are compared with experimental data and numerical results in Section 5.

$$St_{\text{lam,T}} = 0.332 Re_x^{-1/2} Pr^{-0.66} \left[1 - \left(\frac{\xi}{x} \right)^{3/4} \right]^{-1/3} \quad (5)$$

$$St_{\text{turb,T}} = 0.0287 Re_x^{-1/5} Pr^{-0.40} \left[1 - \left(\frac{\xi}{x} \right)^{9/10} \right]^{-1/9} \quad (6)$$

A slip and adiabatic region before the rough plate is incorporated from $x = -1016$ mm up to $x = 0$ mm. The top wall of the entire flow domain is set as a symmetry condition (slip and adiabatic wall), as well as the side walls of the Laminar and the RANS subdomains, while the side walls of the LES subdomain are set as spanwise periodic interfaces.⁴ A homogeneous flow with velocity U_∞ , temperature $T_\infty < T_w$, and no turbulent content enters the flow domain via the Inlet. Results have

⁴ Setting the side walls of the Laminar and RANS subdomains to spanwise periodic interfaces as with the LES does not have any impact on the numerical results in the LES subdomain, which covers the region of interest.

Fig. 5. δ_{lam} and δ_{turb} vs. Re_x . Vertical dashed lines (--) correspond to the locations of the interfaces.

shown that turbulence eventually develops due to roughness inside the LES subdomain due to a roughness-induced transition of the boundary layer. Since the flow presents a ZPG, the Outlet is set at zero relative static pressure as the Inlet.

A boundary layer thickness δ is estimated following Eqs. (7) and Eqs. (8) for a laminar and turbulent boundary layer over a smooth plate [29], respectively. The thickness evolution along the plate length is presented in Fig. 5. The estimation delivers a $\delta_{\text{turb}} = 31$ mm at the LES-RANS interface, implying a $\Delta H/\delta_{\text{turb}} \approx 9.7$ at this position, and indicating that the ΔH from the experimental setup is sufficient for the simulations to avoid boundary layer constraining. In addition, δ_{turb} needs to be considered when choosing ΔZ , and this aspect is analyzed in detail in Section 3.2.

$$\delta_{\text{lam}} = 4.91 Re_x^{-1/2} x \quad (7)$$

$$\delta_{\text{turb}} = 0.38 Re_x^{-1/5} x \quad (8)$$

By subdividing the rough plate in streamwise sub-regions of extension $\Delta x_{\text{div}} = 25.4$ mm ($\Delta Re_x = 0.103 \cdot 10^5$), the r.m.s. of the spatial fluctuations of the rough geometry R_q was obtained at each sub-region as described in Sotomayor-Zakharov et al. [18]. Summarizing this method, R_q is computed at the x center position x_p of a specific sub-region via Eq. (9), where h is the location in the y coordinate of the rough surface and h_m is the mean location in the y coordinate of the rough surface in the current sub-region, computed via Eq. (10).

$$R_q(x_p) = \left[\frac{1}{\Delta x_{\text{div}} \Delta Z} \int_{x_p - \frac{\Delta x_{\text{div}}}{2}}^{x_p + \frac{\Delta x_{\text{div}}}{2}} \int_{z_{\text{min}}}^{z_{\text{max}}} (h(x, z) - h_m(x_p))^2 dx dz \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (9)$$

$$h_m(x_p) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_{\text{div}} \Delta Z} \int_{x_p - \frac{\Delta x_{\text{div}}}{2}}^{x_p + \frac{\Delta x_{\text{div}}}{2}} \int_{z_{\text{min}}}^{z_{\text{max}}} h(x, z) dx dz \quad (10)$$

Fig. 6 presents the R_q vs. Re_x distributions over the rough plate of the investigated surfaces. By using R_q to quantify roughness levels, it can be observed that the roughness starts to slightly manifest at a location of $Re_x \approx 0.7 \cdot 10^5$, being this a distance of more than $20\delta_{\text{lam}}$ from the Laminar-LES interface. On the other hand, roughness almost vanishes at $Re_x \approx 4 \cdot 10^5$, being this position located at slightly more than $4\delta_{\text{turb}}$ from the LES-RANS interface. Also, surface 113012.05 displays lower roughness levels in contrast to surface 113012.04, explaining the differences that heat transfer measurements present in Fig. 3. Indeed, a more rough surface would imply a higher heat transfer enhancement in contrast to a smooth surface.

2.3. Mesh characteristics

An adaptive cartesian mesh is generated in the LES subdomain, with cubic elements that progressively halve their edge size as they approach the boundary corresponding to the rough plate, resulting in different mesh level resolutions. The maximum mesh level starting at the top wall presents an edge size in x , y , and z directions of $\Delta l_{\text{max}} = 6.4$ mm

Fig. 6. R_q vs. Re_x of investigated surfaces. Vertical dashed lines (--) correspond to the locations of the interfaces.

Fig. 7. Mesh structure used for the LES subdomain. The mesh gets refined as it approaches the rough plate.

(= $\Delta x_{\text{max}} = \Delta y_{\text{max}} = \Delta z_{\text{max}}$). At the rough wall, an edge size of $\Delta l_{\text{res}} = 0.4$ mm (= $\Delta x_{\text{res}} = \Delta y_{\text{res}} = \Delta z_{\text{res}}$) was selected for the minimum mesh level, acting as the scale for the surface discretization. This results in 5 mesh levels, as shown in Fig. 7. Close to the rough plate, the cartesian mesh merges with a body-fitted boundary layer mesh, which presents a first layer thickness $\Delta y_{\text{min}} = 0.02$ mm and a geometrical growth ratio of 1.15. The number of layers was selected by trying to match the last layer of the boundary layer mesh to half of Δl_{res} .

Additionally, while moving streamwise, the finer levels of the cartesian mesh tend to cover a bigger portion of the subdomain, accounting for the boundary layer growth, as shown in Fig. 8, which presents contours of time-averaged non-dimensional velocity $|\bar{u}|/U_\infty$ on an x - y plane cut of the LES subdomain of the case with the highest roughness levels (case 2, see Section 3.2). It can be seen that the boundary layer mainly resides in the 4th and 5th mesh levels, the finest of the LES subdomain.

The Laminar and RANS subdomains are discretized with hexahedral elements, which grow geometrically in the y direction from a first layer thickness $\Delta y_{\text{min}} = 0.02$ mm at the slip region, rough plate and plate extension until a $\Delta y = 6.4$ mm, keeping this size until reaching the top wall. Both domains present a spanwise discretization of $\Delta z = 6.25$ mm. Also, in the Laminar subdomain, the mesh grows geometrically streamwise from $x = 0$ mm, from a value of $\Delta x = 0.8$ mm until reaching $\Delta x = 6.4$ mm at the Laminar-LES interface. On the other direction, from the interface towards the inlet, it grows from $\Delta x = 0.8$ mm to values of $\Delta x \approx 50$ mm. In the RANS subdomain, the mesh grows geometrically streamwise from the LES-RANS interface starting with a value of $\Delta x = 6.4$ mm towards a value of $\Delta x \approx 150$ mm at the outlet. It is noted that an analysis of the effect of the LES-RANS interface on the results is presented in Appendix. Both the Laminar and RANS subdomains present around 10^5 mesh elements, this being 1% of the amount of mesh elements present in the LES subdomain.

The listed quantities are scaled in wall units relative to the case in analysis, being these presented in Table 2 in Section 3.2.

Fig. 8. Contours of $|\bar{u}|/U_\infty$, along with mesh level distribution of the LES subdomain of case 2 (see Section 3.2). Black lines indicate the limits between mesh levels. The finer mesh levels normally grow from the rough plate while moving streamwise to account for the boundary layer growth.

Table 2

Test cases for numerical simulations.

ID	Elements	Δt_{res} (Levels)	Δt_{res}^+	Δy_{min}^+	$R_{q,max}^+$	ΔZ (SF)
1	$11.0 \cdot 10^6$	0.4 mm (5)	4–20	0.1–0.5	70	50 mm (24%)
1-Ext.	$22.4 \cdot 10^6$	0.4 mm (5)	4–20	0.1–0.5	70	100 mm (12%)
1-Doub.	$22.0 \cdot 10^6$	0.4 mm (5)	4–20	0.1–0.5	70	100 mm (24%)
1-Coar.	$3.3 \cdot 10^6$	0.8 mm (4)	9–40	0.1–0.5	70	50 mm (24%)
1-Fine	$36.6 \cdot 10^6$	0.2 mm (6)	2–10	0.1–0.5	70	50 mm (24%)
2	$11.8 \cdot 10^6$	0.4 mm (5)	4–30	0.1–0.8	265	50 mm (24%)
1- ξ	$11.0 \cdot 10^6$	0.4 mm (5)	4–20	0.1–0.5	70	50 mm (24%)
2- ξ	$11.8 \cdot 10^6$	0.4 mm (5)	4–30	0.1–0.8	265	50 mm (24%)

2.4. Numerical schemes

The ELES was performed considering an incompressible flow with constant properties, using the software ANSYS FLUENT 21R2. The intended physics to be solved are modeled via the Navier–Stokes equations presented in Eq. (11) for the momentum transport and in Eq. (12) for the thermal transport, where u_i is the flow velocity in the i direction, p is the flow static pressure and $\theta = T_w - T$ is the flow relative temperature. This last property is treated as a passive scalar, therefore, having no influence on the momentum transport.

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u_i u_j}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\mu}{\rho} \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial x_j^2} \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u_j \theta}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\lambda}{\rho c_p} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial x_j^2} \quad (12)$$

The Laminar subdomain does not present any turbulence model, and, given the absence of Inlet turbulence content, the boundary layer will remain laminar up to the Laminar-LES interface ($Re_x = 0.41 \cdot 10^5$), solving Eqs. (11) and (12) in their current form. The RANS subdomain uses the SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model [30] therefore modifying Eqs. (11) and (12) into RANS form. A constant turbulent Prandtl number of $Pr_t = c_p \mu_t / \lambda_t = 0.85$ is used to calculate the turbulent thermal conductivity λ_t from the eddy viscosity μ_t . The LES subdomain uses the WALE subgrid-scale (SGS) model of Nicoud and Ducros [31], therefore modifying Eqs. (11) and (12) into explicit LES form, allowing the solution of the flow field down to the surface without any extra roughness models, resulting in a wall-resolved LES. The study of Sotomayor-Zakharov [25] carries a numerical scheme analysis and validation on canonical cases, from which a subgrid-scale constant $C_w = 0.325$ is selected, as well as a SGS Prandtl number $Pr_{sgs} = c_p \mu_{sgs} / \lambda_{sgs} = 0.85$ to calculate the SGS thermal conductivity λ_{sgs} from the SGS viscosity μ_{sgs} . This numerical schemes analysis establishes as well the usage of the non-iterative time advancement (NITA) solver with 2nd order implicit transient scheme [32], pressure-implicit with splitting operators (PISO) scheme for pressure-velocity coupling with neighbor correction [32], a 2nd order pressure scheme and a bounded central difference (BCD) scheme for convective terms, with a BCD boundedness parameter of

Fig. 9. Variation of mean values of c_f and St vs. t' inside the LES subdomain for case 1 (see Section 3.2). Vertical dashed lines (–) correspond to the initial time t'_i for sampling of flow statistics.

0.7 [33]. Lastly, the least-squares cell-based method is employed for the computation of spatial gradients.

The ELES simulation is initialized from the results of a RANS simulation using the SST $k-\omega \gamma-Re_\theta$ transition model [34] in the whole flow domain.⁵ The converged RANS solution is perturbed to excite the initial development of turbulent content. This strategy is based on a synthetic turbulence generation technique provided by the solver [35], which generates a perturbed velocity field out of steady-state RANS results and it is used to reduce the time needed for the simulation to reach a statistically stable state. The ELES simulations are computed with a time-step Δt that guarantees a maximum CFL < 0.5 , corresponding to a non-dimensional time-step $\Delta t' = U_\infty \Delta t / L \approx 1.75 \cdot 10^{-5}$. The computations were carried with a flow-time $t'_1 = U_\infty t_1 / L \approx 2$, which was long enough until averageable behavior could be observed on flow properties, such as on the mean values of c_f and St computed from the LES subdomain, as shown in Fig. 9 (obtained from case 1, see Section 3.2). Once this state was reached, flow statistics started to be computed during an extra amount of flow-time $t'_S = U_\infty t_S / L \approx 2.5$.

2.5. Analysis of wall properties

The wall properties are computed from time-averaged flow properties at the rough surface. These quantities are obtained through the operation presented in Eq. (13), where $\bar{\psi}$ is the time-average during a period t_S of an arbitrary property ψ .

$$\bar{\psi}(x, y, z) = \frac{1}{t_S} \int_{t_I}^{t_I+t_S} \psi(x, y, z, t) dt \quad (13)$$

Therefore, the time-averaged pressure \bar{p} , shear stress $\bar{\tau}$, and heat flux \bar{q} are extracted on the rough surface and then applied in Eq. (14) to

⁵ The transition model is exploited to initialize the ELES with an already solved laminar boundary layer up to the position where roughness starts to appear.

Fig. 10. R_q vs. Re_x of cases based on ΔZ . Vertical dashed lines (--) correspond to the locations of the interfaces.

compute τ_w and in Eq. (15) to compute q_w . Here, A_w corresponds to the wetted area of the rough surface in the current sub-region, $\bar{\tau}_x$ is the x direction component of $\bar{\tau}$, and η_x is the x direction component of the normal of dA_w .

$$\tau_w(x_p) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_{\text{div}} \Delta Z} \int_{A_w} (\bar{\tau}_x - \bar{p} \eta_x) dA_w \quad (14)$$

$$q_w(x_p) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_{\text{div}} \Delta Z} \int_{A_w} \bar{q} dA_w \quad (15)$$

Finally, c_f and St are calculated for each sub-region via Eqs. (16) and (17), respectively, where $\Delta T = T_w - T_\infty$. Following Eq. (1), the definition of $HTC = q_w / \Delta T$ can be retrieved.

$$c_f = \frac{2 \tau_w}{\rho_\infty U_\infty^2} \quad (16)$$

$$St = \frac{q_w}{\rho c_p U_\infty \Delta T} \quad (17)$$

2.6. Analysis of flow statistics

The analysis of the flow statistics is performed through the extraction of boundary layer profiles in the y direction at locations x_p with the intention of matching the profile with extracted wall properties for scaling at each sub-region. Therefore, the operation $\langle \psi \rangle$ is presented for an arbitrary time-averaged property $\bar{\psi}$, which stands for plane-averaging in the x and z directions.

$$\langle \psi(x_p, y) \rangle = \frac{1}{\Delta x_{\text{div}} \Delta Z} \int_{x_p - \frac{\Delta x_{\text{div}}}{2}}^{x_p + \frac{\Delta x_{\text{div}}}{2}} \int_{z_{\text{min}}}^{z_{\text{max}}} \bar{\psi}(x, y, z) dx dz \quad (18)$$

Properties on the boundary layer profiles such as the velocity $\langle u \rangle^+$, temperature $\langle \theta \rangle^+$, and Reynolds and thermal stresses are scaled in wall units, indicated by the superscript (+), by means of the friction velocity u_τ and temperature T_τ , which are computed at each sub-region via Eqs. (19) and (20), respectively.

$$u_\tau = \sqrt{\frac{\tau_w}{\rho}} \quad (19)$$

$$T_\tau = \frac{q_w}{\rho c_p u_\tau} \quad (20)$$

The wall-distance y^+ is scaled via Eq. (21), noting that h_m is taken into account to represent that the profile begins at the mean roughness height of the sub-region.

$$y^+ = \frac{\rho u_\tau (y - h_m)}{\mu} \quad (21)$$

3. Test cases

3.1. Flow properties

Based on the data of McCarrell et al. [26], temperatures of $T_\infty = 295$ K at the freestream and $T_w = 305$ K at the wall were selected for the current study. This leads to a bulk temperature $T_b = 0.5(T_w + T_\infty) = 300$ K, from which the air properties are estimated and presented in Table 1. Such selection of parameters implies a temperature difference of $\Delta T = 10$ K at the wall. Properties as ρ , c_p , μ and λ are kept constant after verifying that their change is around $\pm 1.7\%$, $\pm 0.0\%$, $\pm 1.3\%$ and $\pm 1.5\%$ for a ± 5 K variation of T_b , respectively. Additionally, a Prandtl number $Pr = 0.729$ is obtained, as well as a Reynolds number based on the reference length of $Re_L = 3.85 \cdot 10^5$ and a Mach number of $Ma_\infty = 0.02$ justifying the incompressible flow assumption.

3.2. Selected cases

The test cases considered for the present investigation are summarized in Table 2, where their designation (ID) is displayed. Case 1 is based on the experimental geometry 113012.05, case 2 is based on 113012.04, and these are considered the reference cases. The selection of a small ΔZ is encouraged to spare computational costs. Initially, the reference cases 1 and 2 are selected with a $\Delta Z = 50$ mm, covering a portion of the original geometry from $z_{\text{max}} = 25$ mm to $z_{\text{min}} = -25$ mm. However, two important aspects must be taken into consideration and are subjected to analysis.

The first aspect relates to the effect of ΔZ over R_q distributions. Since the original experimental geometries present a total span of $\Delta Z = 203.2$ mm (see Section 2.1), the selection of a smaller ΔZ has the potential of affecting flow properties if certain surface features are removed by this reduction or smoothed by any other additional procedure. This removal or smoothing can be observed by comparing the R_q distributions of the total span geometry with the one with a smaller ΔZ . To analyze the effect that the selection of ΔZ has on the flow properties, case 1-Ext. (Extended) with a $\Delta Z = 100$ mm is established ($z_{\text{max}} = 50$ mm to $z_{\text{min}} = -50$ mm), effectively presenting twice the span than the reference case. Fig. 10 is presented, showing the effect of the choice of ΔZ on the distributions of R_q across Re_x . It can be seen that the reference cases present lower values of R_q , while case 1-Ext. presents values closer to the trend of the original geometry. The main reason behind the differences between R_q of the cases and the original geometry is an artificial procedure performed on the flow domain construction to ensure that the side walls of the LES subdomain would match for periodicity: the rough geometry close to the side walls is smoothed towards values of the local mean geometrical height in the y direction using a sinusoidal function as a filter in the z direction. The size of the filter at each side is $\Delta Z_{\text{filter}} = 6$ mm, which showed proper smoothing and good geometrical behavior. This implies that a fraction of the span of $SF = 2 \Delta Z_{\text{filter}} / \Delta Z$ is affected by the filter, being $SF = 24\%$ for $\Delta Z = 50$, resulting in a smoothing effect close to the side walls, and ultimately reducing R_q . The effect of the filter is mitigated as a larger $\Delta Z = 100$ mm is chosen, resulting in a $SF = 12\%$. This leads to lesser R_q decay, which is analyzed in case 1-Ext. On the other hand, further reduction of the span below $\Delta Z = 50$ would imply an increase on SF , which, for example, could reach values of 48% for a $\Delta Z = 25$ mm, having almost half of the domain filtered. It is noted that a second reason for the R_q difference could be due to a strong reduction of ΔZ below representative spatial wavelengths that form the roughness on the surface. The previously selected values of ΔZ are not small enough for this effect to be prominent in comparison to the smoothing effect, although both affect the final R_q distribution, potentially presenting an effect on flow properties such as the HTC .

The second aspect relates to the effect of ΔZ over turbulence since small constraining span values may not allow the proper development of turbulent content on the boundary layer. The reference cases present

Fig. 11. Cases with different mesh resolution Δl_{res} . (a) Case 1-Coar. (b) Case 1 (reference). (c) Case 1-Fine.

$\Delta Z = 50$ mm, which results in a $\Delta Z/\delta_{turb} \approx 1.6$ at the LES-RANS interface, and a $\Delta Z/\delta_{turb} \approx 2.5$ at the middle of the LES subdomain, where roughness is prominent. This ΔZ is expected to be sufficient to capture the development of spanwise turbulence structures according to previous numerical and experimental studies. For example, Lund et al. [36] used a $\Delta Z/\delta_{turb} \approx \pi/2$ at the center of a LES ZPG turbulent boundary layer, while experiments from Tomkins and Adrian [37] found evidence of large structures in the logarithmic layer extending up to $0.6\delta_{turb}$ spanwise. Case 1-Ext. with a $\Delta Z = 100$ mm ($\Delta Z/\delta_{turb} \approx 3.2$) could be used to prove this aspect by comparing it to Case 1. However, the previously stated change on R_q introduced by the spanwise extension could mislead the comparison of the resulting flow properties and statistics between case 1-Ext. and case 1. Therefore, to isolate the effect of ΔZ on turbulent flow statistics, case 1-Doub. (Double) is introduced, resulting from the pairing of two identical case 1 geometries next to each other spanwise. This implies a $\Delta Z = 100$, which preserves the same R_q vs. Re_x distribution as case 1, allowing the comparison of turbulent properties under domains with a different span but with the same roughness effects.

In addition to the span analysis, a mesh study is carried out with a coarser and refined version of case 1, designated as case 1-Coar. and case 1-Fine, respectively. The coarsening/refinement is controlled by modifying the Δl_{res} to twice/half its original value, resulting in the meshes shown in Fig. 11, which show the different cartesian mesh refinement levels. It was analyzed that at these resolutions, the choice of Δl_{res} does not have any notable effect over R_q distributions due to the effect of surface meshing.

Finally, all previously stated cases consider that the entire rough plate and its extension are at T_w . Nevertheless, cases 1- ξ and 2- ξ are introduced with an unheated length of $\xi = 44$ mm as in the experiments to assess its effect on the results, treating the region between $x = 0$ mm and $x = 44$ mm as adiabatic.

4. Verification

4.1. Effect of mesh resolution Δl_{res}

The influence of Δl_{res} on the results is analyzed by comparing case 1 with case 1-Coar. and case 1-Fine. Fig. 12 presents computed values of c_f and St vs. Re_x across cases. As a reference, the c_f vs. Re_x distribution for a laminar (Eq. (22)) and turbulent (Eq. (23)) boundary layer over a smooth plate is presented, as well as the St vs. Re_x distributions for a laminar (Eq. (5)) and turbulent (Eq. (6)) boundary layer over a smooth plate at a constant temperature. It can be seen that as Δl_{res} is refined, the distributions of c_f and St tend to converge, being the greatest differences between mesh levels located at $Re_x \approx 1.8 \cdot 10^5$, corresponding to the location of the highest values of R_q (see Fig. 6). All curves show that a laminar boundary layer is initially formed, which matches the theoretical smooth wall values and manages to cross the Laminar-LES interface ($Re_x = 0.41 \cdot 10^5$). Transition to turbulence is induced by roughness inside the LES subdomain after $Re_x = 1 \cdot 10^5$, resulting in c_f and St distributions with values above theoretical smooth ones for turbulent flow. As R_q decreases approaching the LES-RANS interface,

Fig. 12. Influence of the mesh resolution Δl_{res} on c_f and St . Vertical dashed lines (-) correspond to the locations of the interfaces.

Table 3
Variation of c_f and St with mesh refinement.

ID	Mean(c_f)	Mean(St)
1-Coar.	0.00717	0.00320
1	0.00737	0.00328
Var.(%)	2.76	2.45
1-Fine	0.00750	0.00334
Var.(%)	1.68	1.71

the turbulent flow recovers its smooth status, and wall properties match again the expected smooth distribution.

$$c_{f,lam} = 0.664 Re_x^{-1/2} \quad (22)$$

$$c_{f,turb} = 0.0574 Re_x^{-1/5} \quad (23)$$

A quantification of the variation of the wall properties between a refined level with its respective coarser level is presented in Table 3, showing the mean values of c_f and St computed inside the LES subdomain. The variations of the mean values decrease as the mesh resolution is refined, demonstrating that the resolution of case 1 is appropriate for the study of the overall roughness effects on the flow.

A qualitative analysis of the turbulent flow behavior is carried on between locations $Re_x = 1.8 \cdot 10^5$ and $Re_x = 2.0 \cdot 10^5$. Fig. 13 displays contours of non-dimensional instantaneous velocity $|u|/U_\infty$ and time-averaged velocity $|\bar{u}|/U_\infty$ at the mid-plane of the flow domain ($z = 0$ mm). It can be observed through $|u|/U_\infty$ that as the mesh resolution is increased, more detailed fluctuating behavior is captured. Separation regions are observed after each roughness peak, and the highly packed roughness elements seem to not allow the flow to recover after separation, a behavior reported for d-type roughness [38–40]. From $|\bar{u}|/U_\infty$, it can be seen that the left separation bubble is affected

Fig. 13. Contours of non-dimensional flow velocity for different mesh resolutions in the region of $Re_x = 1.8 \cdot 10^5$ to $Re_x = 2.0 \cdot 10^5$ and $z = 0$ mm. Left column: Instantaneous values $|u|/U_\infty$. Right column: Time-averaged values $|\bar{u}|/U_\infty$.

Fig. 14. Contours of non-dimensional flow temperature for different mesh resolutions in the region of $Re_x = 1.8 \cdot 10^5$ to $Re_x = 2.0 \cdot 10^5$ and $z = 0$ mm. Left column: Instantaneous values θ/θ_∞ . Right column: Time-averaged values $\bar{\theta}/\theta_\infty$.

Table 4
Locations for the extraction of boundary layer profiles.

ID	x [mm]	$Re_x \cdot 10^{-5}$ [-]
1	444.5	1.8
2	622.3	2.5
3	800.1	3.2
4	977.9	4.0
5	1079.5	4.4

by the mesh resolution between case 1-Coar. and case 1, justifying the difference of c_f at $Re_x = 1.8 \cdot 10^5$ between these cases. In contrast, case 1 and case 1-Fine present similar flow characteristics, which results in the lower differences of c_f between these cases observed in Fig. 12 and in Table 3.

To analyze the temperature fields between $Re_x = 1.8 \cdot 10^5$ and $Re_x = 2.0 \cdot 10^5$, Fig. 14 is presented, displaying contours of non-dimensional instantaneous relative temperature θ/θ_∞ and time-averaged relative temperature $\bar{\theta}/\theta_\infty$ ($\theta_\infty = T_w - T_\infty$) at the mid-plane of the flow domain ($z = 0$ mm). As observed for the velocity fields, an increase in mesh resolution manages to capture more detailed behavior of spatial fluctuations of θ/θ_∞ . Still, contours of $\bar{\theta}/\theta_\infty$ display a consistent behavior at different mesh resolutions, indicating small temperature gradients inside separation regions after roughness elements, while the highest temperature gradients are observed at the roughness peaks.

By performing an analysis of the flow statistics, the boundary layer profiles in the y direction across the flow domain are extracted at the x locations listed in Table 4.

Fig. 15. Mean turbulent profiles at different mesh resolutions. Dashed lines (--) indicate the theoretical smooth plate velocity and temperature log-layers.

Profiles of $\langle u \rangle^+$ and $\langle \theta \rangle^+$ are displayed in Fig. 15 for the three considered mesh resolutions, showing no major effects on almost all the profiles except on the 1st one, which presents higher values of $\langle u \rangle^+$ for case 1-Coar. This can be related to the lower c_f prediction at $Re_x = 1.8 \cdot 10^5$ associated with such case. Still, the velocity and thermal shifts with respect to the log-law are clearly visible on the 2nd and 3rd profiles, as evidence of the roughness influence over the boundary layer, being this shift similar across mesh resolutions.

The mean Reynolds and thermal stresses are analyzed in Fig. 16. Here, only the 2nd and 5th profiles are displayed, located in the rough zone and smooth zone, respectively, allowing the analysis of the impact of roughness on the flow statistics. The normal stresses $\langle u'^2 \rangle^+$, $\langle v'^2 \rangle^+$, $\langle w'^2 \rangle^+$ and $\langle \theta'^2 \rangle^+$ display a similar behavior at different resolutions for both profiles. Nevertheless, the 5th profile exhibits the expected anisotropic behavior close to the wall on smooth surfaces, where $\langle u'^2 \rangle^+ > \langle w'^2 \rangle^+ > \langle v'^2 \rangle^+$, reported by several studies as in Jiménez [39]. The 2nd profile exhibits the tendency to isotropy that roughness forces into the turbulent field, with $\langle u'^2 \rangle^+ \approx \langle w'^2 \rangle^+ \approx \langle v'^2 \rangle^+$. Specifically, the damping of the peak of $\langle u'^2 \rangle^+$ is prominent due to the constraining nature of the roughness over the spanwise fluctuations, which is associated with the destruction of the buffer layer caused by the intrusion of large roughness elements, as also stated by Yuan and Piomelli [41]. Similar trends have been observed in the literature on sand-grain roughness by Cardillo et al. [19] and Yuan and Piomelli [20]. In the case of $\langle \theta'^2 \rangle^+$, a similar damping of the peak value due to roughness is observed, although its value increases around $y/\delta_\theta = 0.5$. The shear component $\langle u'v' \rangle^+$ reveals sensitivity to the mesh on the 5th profile, possibly indicating a slightly different tendency to recover after the rough zone dictated by the different mesh resolutions. In particular, $\langle u'v' \rangle^+$ is uniformly reduced across the boundary layer at the 2nd profile in contrast to the 5th one, manifesting once again the influence of increased local friction due to roughness. On the other hand, $\langle v'\theta' \rangle^+$ shows similar peak values between the 2nd and 5th profile, although with a shifted peak location away from the wall due to roughness effects.

Overall, the mesh resolution of case 1 manages to discretize the relevant spatial wavelengths of the rough surface and capture its interactions with the flow field, as well as not presenting strong variations on flow properties such as c_f and St distributions and turbulence statistics through further mesh refinement. This implies that this mesh level can be used for further analysis in the current study.

4.2. Effect of domain span ΔZ

The effect of ΔZ is analyzed by comparing the results of case 1 with case 1-Ext. and case 1-Doub. It is worth reminding that ΔZ can have mainly two effects on the results, namely the constriction of turbulent

Fig. 16. Mean Reynolds and thermal stresses at different mesh resolutions. Only the 2nd (—) and 5th profile (---) are displayed. The wall distance is scaled with respect to the local boundary layer thickness, δ_{99} or δ , and thermal boundary layer thickness, δ_θ .

Fig. 17. Influence of the domain span ΔZ on c_f and St . Vertical dashed lines (---) correspond to the locations of the interfaces.

content due to a small ΔZ in relation to δ , and variation on the values of c_f or St due to different R_q distributions. Fig. 17 presents the results for c_f and St vs. Re_x distributions of case 1, case 1-Doub., and case 1-Ext., together with theoretical values described by Eqs. (22), (23), (5) and (6). Case 1 and case 1-Doub. do not exhibit any notable differences, implying that $\Delta Z = 50$ mm allows the correct development of turbulent flow fields, although a detailed analysis of flow statistics is necessary to fully support this statement. On the other hand, case 1 and case 1-Ext. display differences due to their different R_q distributions, more prominent for c_f in contrast to St , although the trends and orders of magnitude remain similar. Maximum peak values can be observed around $Re_x = 1.8 \cdot 10^5$ for all cases, with a recovery towards a smooth behavior around $Re_x = 4 \cdot 10^5$, where $\Delta Z/\delta \approx 2$ and still inside the LES subdomain.

Fig. 18. Mean turbulent profiles for different domain spans. Dashed lines (---) indicate the theoretical smooth plate velocity and temperature log-layers.

For a deeper analysis, the flow statistics of case 1, case 1-Doub. and case 1-Ext. are considered. Profiles of $\langle u \rangle^+$ and $\langle \theta \rangle^+$ are presented in Fig. 18. Case 1 and case 1-Doub. present similar profiles. The only sensible difference between these cases and case 1-Ext. is presented by the 1st profile of $\langle u \rangle^+$, corresponding to the zone before the first roughness peak. This is indeed reflected in the difference of the c_f prediction at $Re_x = 1.8 \cdot 10^5$ showed in Fig. 17, where the higher friction captured by increasing the span is resulting in a lower $\langle u \rangle^+$ estimation. The better match in St between the cases is found through the good agreement of the thermal profiles.

Reynolds and thermal stresses are depicted in Fig. 19 for the 2nd and 5th profiles. In general, case 1 and case 1-Doub. display similar values across the stresses, supporting the claim that $\Delta Z = 50$ mm is large enough to sustain unconstrained turbulence development. The differences between case 1 and case 1-Ext. are more significant for the Reynolds stresses compared to the thermal ones. The largest discrepancies are observed in the quantities $\langle u'^2 \rangle^+$ and $\langle u'v' \rangle^+$, where the predictions for case 1 and case 1-Doub. show notable variations. Thermal stresses match fairly well, although presenting the same behavior described in the mesh analysis, where roughness induces $\langle \theta'^2 \rangle^+$ to present reduced peak values next to the wall but larger values around $y/\delta_\theta = 0.5$, while $\langle v'\theta' \rangle^+$ is shifted away from the wall. Once again, these insights justify the use of the numerical setup used for case 1 for further analysis and for validation.

5. Validation

5.1. Comparison with experimental data of c_f

Fig. 20 presents a comparison between the c_f vs. Re_x distributions obtained from case 1 and case 1-Ext. with experimentally measured c_f values,⁶ as well as the theoretical curves described by Eqs. (22) and (23). Qualitative resemblance can be observed between the ELES results, where the two peaks before and after $Re_x = 2 \cdot 10^5$ are captured by the simulations but overestimating their magnitudes. Nevertheless, case 1-Ext. seems to approach experimental results in a better way, being justified by the better description of R_q distributions. Therefore, it can be stated that a main source of inaccuracy of numerical results with respect to the experimental data involves the usage of a ΔZ that does not cover the entire experimental span of $\Delta Z = 203.2$ mm, although this result would remain valid respect to its own topography and R_q distribution.

⁶ In the results figure, the experimental data for c_f was shifted in the x direction an amount of -50.8 mm (2 in), based on discussions with the authors of the experimental study, who indicated that such a shift could exist even though it was not recorded in the paper. Indeed, this adjustment enhanced the qualitative alignment with the numerical results for both analyzed cases.

Fig. 19. Mean Reynolds and thermal stresses for different domain spans. Only the 2nd (---) and 5th profile (—) are displayed. The wall distance is scaled with respect to the local boundary layer thickness, δ_{99} or δ , and thermal boundary layer thickness, δ_θ .

Fig. 20. Comparison of c_f vs. Re_x between numerical results of case 1 and experimentally measured data of McCarrell et al. [26] (113012.05). Vertical dashed lines (---) correspond to the locations of the interfaces.

Considering case 2, Fig. 21 is presented, comparing the experimental and numerical distributions of c_f vs. Re_x . A certain matching trend can be observed, except for the massive c_f peak around $Re_x \approx 2.4 \cdot 10^5$. This can be the consequence of an isolated massive rough element, although distributions of R_q (Fig. 10) do not display any notable peak, but a notable trough upstream close to $Re_x \approx 2 \cdot 10^5$. This might imply that this trough allows the boundary layer to recover and gain momentum after separation before meeting an isolated rough element, a similar behavior to what is observed in k-type roughness [38–40]. Observing Fig. 10, the original full-span geometry does not present this massive trough since it is averaged by other roughness elements across the non-considered span by case 2, which may be a reason for the reduced values of c_f in the experiments, as well as supporting the observation made for case 1.

5.2. Comparison with experimental data of St

Fig. 22 presents several curves of St vs. Re_x for some variants of case 1, as well as theoretical curves corresponding to boundary layers over smooth plates at a constant T_w , for its laminar (Lam-T, Eq. (5))

Fig. 21. Comparison of c_f vs. Re_x between numerical results of case 2 and experimentally measured data of McCarrell et al. [26] (113012.04). Vertical dashed lines (---) correspond to the locations of the interfaces.

Fig. 22. Comparison of St vs. Re_x between numerical results of case 1 and experimentally measured data of McCarrell et al. [26] (113012.05). Vertical dashed lines (---) correspond to the locations of the interfaces.

and fully turbulent (Turb-T, Eq. (6)) form, as well as including the laminar form with an unheated length (Lam-T- ξ , Eq. (5) with $\xi = 44$ mm). The laminar boundary layer over a wall at a constant heat flux and unheated length is presented as well (Lam-HF- ξ , Eq. (3) with $\xi = 44$ mm), which has been shown to match the experimental data at the laminar region (see Fig. 3). By just analyzing case 1 and case 1-Ext., it can be seen that the simulations manage to match the theoretical curves for a smooth plate at constant T_w as long as the boundary layer remains laminar, while still deviating from experimental values due to the nature of the boundary condition as explained in Section 2.2. Nevertheless, roughness-induced transition of the boundary layer drives wall properties up to values above the turbulent smooth plate ones, with St reaching values similar to the experimental ones in the rough region, achieving the expected goal of the present study. Still, case 1-Ext. exhibits larger St values than case 1 around $Re_x = 1.8 \cdot 10^5$, which can be correlated to the larger R_q in this region. Case 1-Ext. mostly exhibits increases on St , implying that the boundary layer recovery effects due to isolated roughness elements described in the analysis of c_f do not play a major role in the physics of heat transfer on rough surfaces.

Similar comments can be made for Fig. 23, which presents the St results of case 2 with the same theoretical curves as the ones presented for case 1. Case 2 manages to match laminar values for a constant T_w before the transition to turbulence. After this, St values on the rough region reach experimental values. Even though c_f displayed a peak value at $Re_x \approx 2.4 \cdot 10^5$, this is not the case for St , where values around this region remain similar without any major features.

From the previous analysis, it can be concluded that differences in the St trends with the experimental data could be associated as well with the different R_q distributions that the cases present in contrast

Fig. 23. Comparison of St vs. Re_x between numerical results of case 1 and experimentally measured data of McCarrell et al. [26] (113012.04). Vertical dashed lines (—) correspond to the locations of the interfaces.

to the original experimental geometry, although this effect is not as dramatic as the one observed in the graphs of c_f , especially when comparing case 1 with case 1-Ext. Another source of inaccuracy can be attributed to the selected boundary condition, being this not the same as the one employed in the experiment (see Section 2.2). Results seem to go over this issue, although a proper analysis considering solid body heat conductivity is required to support this claim. Nevertheless, the close approach towards experimental results showcases the capacity of the employed ELES strategy to capture expected flow behavior related to heat transfer in the presence of roughness.

5.3. Effect of unheated length ξ

Figs. 22 and 23 display as well case 1- ξ and case 2- ξ , respectively. Their trends align with the theoretical curve for a smooth plate at a constant T_w with an initial unheated length ξ (Lam-T- ξ) in the region before the roughness-induced transition takes place. This also evidences that a constant heat flux condition would have allowed a match with the experimental data, at least in the laminar region. Nevertheless, the effect of this unheated length over the resulting St distributions is minimal in the rough regions after the roughness-induced transition takes place, showcased by their similar proximity to experimental values as with their corresponding fully heated rough plate cases.

6. Conclusions

The verification and validation of an ELES setup for the study of boundary layer flow over non-homogeneous ice roughness was successfully performed, using geometries from an experimental database, which include as well measurements of skin friction coefficients c_f and Stanton numbers St .

The verification process included an analysis of the effect of the mesh resolution Δl_{res} on distributions of c_f and St , which showed a convergent behavior as Δl_{res} is refined. Flow statistics also displayed a convergent behavior by keeping a similar trend on profiles located in the rough and smooth regions.

It was confirmed that a flow domain that takes an amount of $\Delta Z = 50$ mm ($\Delta Z/\delta_{turb} \approx 1.6$) of the original experimental geometry allows the proper development of turbulent content. This was inferred from a comparison to a case with $\Delta Z = 100$ mm whose flow domain was constructed by pairing two identical domains of $\Delta Z = 50$ mm next to each other spanwise, effectively preserving the R_q distributions. On the other hand, a comparison was made with a case that takes a $\Delta Z = 100$ mm of the original experimental geometry, resulting in a different R_q distribution that eventually affects the resulting c_f and St over the rough plate, as well as the flow statistics. While no strict lower limit

on ΔZ was identified, further reduction could constrain large coherent structures and the proper description of R_q and the rough surface.

From the previous analysis, it was observed that roughness effects are reflected on the mean velocity and temperature profiles through expected shifts in the log-layer behavior, as well as on the Reynolds and thermal stresses. Normal Reynolds stresses, especially $\langle u'^2 \rangle^+$, are damped in the rough region, showing a tendency towards isotropy, in contrast with the classical anisotropic behavior observed in smooth regions, as showcased in some studies. The shear Reynolds stress shows a damping behavior as well of $\langle u'v' \rangle^+$. The thermal component $\langle v'\theta \rangle^+$ revealed that roughness moves its peak value away from the wall, while the peak value of $\langle \theta'^2 \rangle^+$ close to the wall is reduced, while its values around $y/\delta \approx 0.5$ are increased.

The validation process displayed that the experimental trends of c_f are numerically captured, although with the presence of numerical peaks that do not match experimental data. One possible explanation is that these differences arise from ΔZ not covering the entire span of the original experimental geometry, resulting in a surface with different R_q distributions and, therefore, different physical effects on the flow field. As ΔZ is increased to cover more of the original geometry, a better trend of c_f is obtained due to a better capture of the original R_q distribution. On the other hand, the validation process showed a good match between the resulting St distributions when compared to the experimental data in the rough region after the boundary layer transition. The ELES are able to capture the St increase due to roughness, managing to match experimental values, while the differences on R_q distributions do not seem to have the same impact as the one observed in the c_f results. This implies that the employed methodology can be used for the effective study of heat transfer on ice roughness.

Finally, it was observed that the unheated length presents almost no influence on the St values on the rough region once the boundary layer transition takes place.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Denis Sotomayor-Zakharov: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Riccardo Gaudio:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Mariachiara Gallia:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Fig. A.24. Effect of the LES-RANS Interface location over c_f and St distributions. Vertical dashed lines (---) correspond to the locations of the interfaces at its original positions, while the vertical dashed-dotted line (-.-) corresponds to the LES-RANS interface location for Case 1-Test.

Appendix. LES-RANS interface

An analysis of the effect of the locations of the LES-RANS interfaces on the results is presented in the current appendix. The interface located between the Lamina and the LES subdomain (Lamina-LES) at $x = 101.6$ mm ($Re_x = 0.41 \cdot 10^5$) does not deserve major attention since the flow is laminar at this location and does not present any turbulent content since the inlet conditions are steady over time. This is justified by the smooth behavior that properties such as c_f and St vs. Re_x present across the interface in all the presented results, as well as matching the expected analytical behavior.

On the other hand, the location of the interface between the LES Subdomain and RANS Subdomain might present an influence on computed results due to the transition of mesh resolution and the switch between LES to RANS turbulence modeling at said location. Taking as a reference Case 1, the LES-RANS interface is originally located at $x = 1117.6$ mm ($Re_x = 4.51 \cdot 10^5$), with roughness vanishing at $Re_x \approx 4 \cdot 10^5$, meaning that the interface is located at $4\delta_{turb}$ after roughness. From this, an additional test case (Case 1-Test) was computed, in which the LES-RANS interface was displaced to the position $x = 1397$ mm ($Re_x = 5.65 \cdot 10^5$), being this now a distance of $10\delta_{turb}$ after roughness. Fig. A.24 presents a comparison between obtained c_f and St vs. Re_x for case 1 and case 1-Test. It can be seen that for both cases, the results are almost identical up to each case's respective LES-RANS interface, implying that this interface does not present an effect on the physics of the region of analysis. Still, c_f presents a slight discontinuity at the interface, while St presents a stronger one, although both cases approach each other as they distance from the interface.

Therefore, it can be stated that locating the LES-RANS interface at least at a value of $4\delta_{turb}$ after the region of interest is adequate for the present study.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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